

The Effect of Compensation, Workload, and Work Life Balance on Employee Loyalty with Job Satisfaction as a Moderating Variable

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Abstract

RSUD Bangkinang is a community health service center in Kampar Regency. Community satisfaction with health services is the main goal of this agency. This can be realized if employees have high loyalty to the agency. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to see and analyze how the influence of workload, work life balance and compensation either directly or indirectly on employee loyalty with job satisfaction as a moderating variable. The types of research data are primary data and secondary data obtained through questionnaires, observations and research files. The research sample was 162 nurses at Bangkinang Hospital. The data analysis tool used is SEM using SmartPLS version 3.0. The results of this study conclude that workload, work life balance, and compensation directly have a significant effect on employee loyalty.

Keywords: *Loyalty, Satisfaction, Workload, Work Life Balance, Compensation.*

INTRODUCTION

Employee loyalty is shown by the commitment of employees within the company, organizational commitment can be formed due to several factors both from the organization and from the individual itself. Nursing services in hospitals are an inseparable part of health services as a whole, so that their role greatly determines the quality and image of the hospital (Bachtiar, 2016). Good and bad hospital services are often judged by the knowledge, skills and independent and professional attitudes of a nurse.

Job satisfaction is an emotional state that is pleasant or unpleasant in which employees view their work which is visible in the employee's attitude towards work and everything that is faced in the work environment (Handoko, 2011). Employees who do not get satisfaction will never reach psychological maturity and ultimately have low morale. Workload is also one that can affect employee satisfaction.

Nurse workload is all activities or activities carried out by nurses during their duties in a nursing service unit. The nursing workload in a unit can be estimated by taking into account the components, namely the number of patients treated per day, per month and per year, the condition of the patient, the average patient being treated, direct and indirect actions needed by the patient, the frequency of each action. required and the average time required to carry out the action.

Research conducted by Mahwidhi (2017) shows that workload has a significant positive effect on employee loyalty in Inpatient Installations RSU Dr Soeroto Ngawi. According to Saydam (2010), loyalty development needs to be carried out so that employees have a high concern for the organization, feel they belong to the organization, prevent turnover, improve performance for organizational sustainability, remain motivated, can increase professionalism and work productivity. Creating and maintaining employee job satisfaction is an important effort for companies to maintain employee loyalty. In increasing job satisfaction, currently many organizations are starting to implement work life balance programs. This program is considered important because the company realizes that employees not only face problems at work, but also outside of work.

RSUD Bangkinang is one of the hospitals owned by the Kampar Regency Government in the form of hospitals. On December 19, 2011, the Bangkinang Hospital became a Regional Public Service Agency (BLUD) with the Decree of the Regent of Kampar No.; 060/ORG/303/2011 concerning the determination of the Bangkinang Hospital as a regional work unit in Kampar Regency which applies the full pattern of financial management of the Regional Public Service Agency (PPK-BLUD). Therefore, there are three types of nursing staff at Bangkinang Hospital, namely Civil Servant (PNS) nurses, BLUD and Partners. Of the three employment statuses, there are differences both in terms of rights and obligations. In this study, it was limited only to nurses with BLUD status because they had a non-permanent employment status when compared to the PNS group.

The following is a description of the data on turnover that occurred at the Bangkinang Hospital in 2016-2020.

Table 1: Labor Turn Over Level of Employees at Bangkinang Hospital for the 2016-2020 period

Year	Nurse with BLUD status	Number of Nurses		% LTO
		Enter	Go out	
2016	216	34	20	9.25
2017	230	40	24	10.43
2018	246	50	33	13.41
2019	263	45	37	14.07
2020	271	-	-	-
Average Per Year				9.43

Source: Data on Organization and Staffing of Bangkinang Hospital

From Table 1 above, it can be seen that there is a tendency for nurses with BLUD status or who are said to be employees to leave the Bangkinang Hospital. This is indicated by the increasing percentage of LTO over the last five years with an average annual LTO rate of 9.43%. This condition illustrates the low level of employee job satisfaction which has an impact on the decrease in employee loyalty.

If we look at the factors that affect the job satisfaction of nurses or employees, it is compensation. Based on the results of interviews with several nurses at the Bangkinang Hospital, Researchers found that 8 nurses were less satisfied with the incentives and bonuses they got. There are 5 people (62%) who say there is a lack of rewards for nurses, 3 people (37%) say there is no match between the provision of rewards for the existing workload. This causes dissatisfaction at work and has an impact on the quality of health services that are less than optimal as seen from the presence of nurses who are not on time, the appearance of nurses who are not neat and can have an impact on the loyalty of nurses to the institutions where they work.

The second factor that affects job satisfaction is workload. One of the indicators used to measure workload is the working hours of employees. Based on the results of interviews with the nursing department, it is known that the working hours of nurses at Bangkinang Hospital are divided into 3 shifts, which consist of *shift* The morning shift works for 7 hours from 7.00-14.00, the afternoon shift works 7 hours from 14.00-21.00, and the night shift works 10 hours from 21.00-7.00. From this situation, it shows that the night shift has the longest working time. This explains that the workload conditions between the three shifts have significant differences. Then from the difference in working hours, nurses also get pressure to work, both from the patient side and from the hospital management. The pressure is like the pressure of stress and mental pressure at work. These impacts all lead to not achieving job satisfaction for nurses, of course this will also affect the loyalty of these nurses to the institutions where they work.

The next factor affecting the job satisfaction of an employee or nurse is work-life balance. The existence of various roles that must be carried out by a nurse, this can cause conflict when two or more roles occur at one time, and one role can hinder the implementation of the other roles. When this role conflict occurs, it will cause no work-life balance. As we know that humans are seen as individuals who have many roles in their lives, including the role of the work environment and outside the work environment.

This condition may also be experienced by the nurses who work at the Bangkinang Hospital. Nurses have little time for their personal lives because they are regulated by a tight work schedule, which makes nurses have to be ready to work at any time, so nurses find it difficult to manage time to do personal activities, gather with family and social environment. Problems will arise when nurses fail to balance work time with personal and family life. Roles as workers and roles in personal and family life often lead to conflict, such as long working hours that can reduce time at home so that they can miss personal activities and family togetherness. For this reason, work-family balance or what is known as work-life balance is very important.

Formulation of the problem

Based on the research background that has been described previously, in this study the formulation of the problem as the basis for the research study to be carried out is as follows:

1. Does compensation directly affect employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
2. Does compensation have an indirect effect on employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
3. Does workload directly affect employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
4. Does the workload indirectly affect employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital?
5. Does work-life balance directly affect employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
6. Does work-life balance indirectly affect employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital?
7. Does satisfaction affect employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital?

Research purposes

Based on the formulation of the problem, the objectives to be achieved in this research are to:

1. Testing and analyzing the direct effect of compensation on employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
2. Testing and analyzing the effect of indirect compensation on employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital
3. Test and analyze the effect of workload directly on employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
4. Test and analyze the effect of workload indirectly on employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
5. To examine and analyze the effect of work-life balance directly on employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
6. Examine and analyze the effect of work-life balance indirectly on employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
7. Testing and analyzing the effect of satisfaction on employee loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Compensation

According to Sihotang (2017), compensation is the overall arrangement of remuneration for employees and managers, both in the form of financial and goods and services received by each employee. Then according to Rivai (2010), compensation is something that employees receive as a substitute for their service contribution to the company. And according to Dessler (2010), employee compensation is any form of payment or reward given to employees who work in a company. According to Hasibuan (2013), compensation is all income in the form of money, goods directly or indirectly received by employees in return for services provided to the company.

Basically, people who work also want to earn money to fulfill their needs. For this reason, an employee begins to appreciate hard work and shows more loyalty to the company and that's why the company rewards employee performance by providing compensation. One way of management to improve work performance, motivate and improve employee performance is through compensation (Mathis and Jackson, 2010). Werther and Davis (2013) classify compensation into two general forms, namely:

1. Direct compensation; consisting of basic salary and wages, and incentives and profit sharing.
2. Indirect compensation; in the form of welfare and service programs. Indirect compensation can be grouped into two types: those provided voluntarily by the employer/employer, and those required by law/regulation.

The indicators in providing compensation for employees are certainly different. According to Hasibuan (2013), in general, compensation indicators are:

1. Salary, is money given every month to employees as compensation for their contributions.
2. Wages are rewards given directly to employees based on hours worked.
3. Incentives are financial rewards given directly to employees whose performance exceeds the specified standards.
4. Allowances are compensation given to certain employees in return for their sacrifices.
5. Facilities are supporting facilities provided by the organization.

Workload

According to Tarwaka (2010) workload can be defined as a difference between the capacity or ability of workers and the demands of the work that must be faced. Considering that human work is mental and physical, each has a different level of loading. The level of loading that is too high allows the use of excessive energy and overstress occurs, on the contrary the intensity of the load that is too low allows boredom and saturation or understress. Workload is the average activity frequency of each job within a certain period of time (Irwandy, 2017). Workload includes physical and mental workload. As a result of a workload that is too heavy or physical abilities that are too weak, it can cause an employee to suffer from work-related disorders or diseases. Basically the workload is one of the elements that must be considered for a workforce to get compatibility and high work productivity in addition to the additional burden element due to the work environment and work capacity (Sudiharto, 2011). The workload that can cause stress is divided into two (Sitepu, 2013):

1. *Role overload*. Role overload occurs when demands exceed the capacity of a manager or employee to adequately meet these demands.
2. *Role underload*. Role underload is a job where the demands faced are below the capacity of an employee.

The workload factor can be seen from 3 aspects, namely physical, mental and use of time. Physical aspects include workloads based on human physical criteria. The mental aspect is the calculation of the workload by considering the mental (psychological) aspect. While the aspect of time utilization is more concerned with the aspect of using time for work (Adipradana, 2018). Workload is strongly influenced by factors directly related to work capacity. According to Tarwaka (2010) the three main factors that determine the workload are task demands, effort and performance.

1. Task demand factor. The argument related to this factor is that the workload can be determined from the analysis of the tasks performed by the workers. However, individual differences must always be taken into account.
2. Effort or energy. The amount spent on a job may be a naturally intuitive form of workload. However, since the task demands increase, individuals may not be able to increase their level of effort.
3. performance. Most studies on workloads are concerned with the level of performance to be achieved. However, performance measurement alone will not be able to provide a complete workload matrix.

Same with Anita's opinion, Nasir and Mukhlis (2013) explain the workload above, it can be concluded that the workload is a series of activities that must be completed by an organizational unit or position holder within a certain period of time. According to Murti and Veronika (2013) workload is a collection or number of activities that must be completed by an organizational unit or position holder within a certain period of time. Workload indicators include:

1. Continuous improvement at work
2. Improving the quality of work
3. Attitude towards employees
4. Understanding the basic substance of work
5. Work ethic
6. Behavior at work
7. Complete challenging tasks
8. Physical conditions of the workplace, and attitude towards time

Work Life Balance

Marks and MacDermid (2011) describe work-life balance as an individual's tendency to be truly committed to performing in each role he or she undertakes. This is in line with what was stated by Greenhaus, Collins and Shaw (2013) that work-life balance is the extent to which individuals feel bound and satisfied with their work life and family life and are able to balance work and family demands. Paluan (2018) added, work-life balance is a concept of balancing roles between career and lifestyle, namely health, happiness, family and spiritual development. In his research it is said that work-life balance occurs when individuals can create appropriate roles at work and in the family with low levels of role conflict.

In line with that, Gregory and Milner (2009) state that work-life balance includes employee time management, inter-role conflict and concern for family. Work-life balance contains three important elements, namely setting the total working hours, responsibilities in taking care of the household and child care. When the role of the family is carried out properly, the workplace will be a pleasant place and employees tend to avoid conflict (McDonald, Brown & Bradley, 2015; Gregory & Milner 2009). Greenhaus, Collins and Shaw (2013) identified three aspects of work-life balance, namely:

1. *Time Balance*. Balance the amount of time an individual spends fulfilling the demands of work and family roles. In this case, the balance of time owned by employees determines the amount of time allocated by employees on their work and personal life with their families. Thus, employees do not feel burdened by work that can reduce their time together with family. In addition, employees can still complete their work professionally without family demands that take up too much of their time.
2. *Involvement Balance*. The balance of individual psychological involvement in meeting the demands of roles in work and family. In this case, when employees can be physically and emotionally involved in their work and family, an involvement balance will be achieved.
3. *Satisfaction Balance*. The balance of individual satisfaction against the demands of roles in work and family. In this case, employee satisfaction will arise if the employee considers that what he has done so far is quite good and can accommodate work and family needs.

According to Bradley (2005) in Ramadhani (2013) there are three indicators in work life balance, namely as follows:

1. Time Balance. Focuses on the balance of time given on and off work. Time balance means the amount of time a person gets when working and activities outside of work. Time balance is a way that can be used to balance time between relaxing or working and resting effectively. The expected results with time balance are increased job satisfaction, better time organization and reduced stress.
2. Balance of Engagement. Focusing on equality in psychological involvement in work and roles outside of work, so that they can enjoy their time and be physically and emotionally involved in social activities.
3. Balance of satisfaction both in the work environment and outside of work. Focuses on the level of balance of a person's satisfaction at work and outside work. Satisfaction will arise if someone can accommodate the needs of work and outside of work well. This can be seen from family conditions, relationships between co-workers and the quality and quantity of work that has been completed. To see the balance of satisfaction, it can be seen with satisfaction with oneself and fulfillment of expectations.

Job satisfaction

Robbins and Mary (2010) suggest that job satisfaction is a general attitude of an individual towards his work. Likewise, Ivancevich (2014) states that job satisfaction is a person's attitude towards their services, that attitude comes from their perception of their work. Likewise with George and Jones (2011) job satisfaction is a collection of feelings, beliefs, and thoughts about how to respond to work. Cognitive aspects of job satisfaction are workers' beliefs about work and work situations. Job satisfaction shows the match between a person's expectations that arise and the rewards provided by the company. Likewise, Davis and Newstrom in Sinambela (2015) he said that some managers assume that high job satisfaction will forever lead to high performance, but this assumption is not true, the evidence gives a more accurate impression that productivity allows satisfaction. Job satisfaction theory tries to reveal what makes some people more satisfied with their jobs than others. Greenberg and Baron (Priansa, 2016) state that the theory of job satisfaction in general is:

1. Two-factor Theory (Two-factor Theory)

Job satisfaction theory describes satisfaction and dissatisfaction from different groups of variables, namely hygiene factors and motivators. Hygiene factors are job dissatisfaction caused by a different set of factors (quality, supervision, work environment, salary payment, security, quality of institutions, work relations and organizational policies.

2. Value Theory

Job satisfaction theory explains the importance of conformity between the work results obtained (awards) with perceptions of the availability of results. The more results he gets, the more satisfied he will be. This theory focuses on the many results obtained. The key to satisfaction is the suitability of the results received with their perceptions.

Research from Spector (2010) states that job satisfaction is related to how employees feel about their work and to various aspects of the job, so job satisfaction is closely related to the extent to which employees are satisfied or dissatisfied with their work. And he can identify job satisfaction indicators from nine aspects, namely:

1. Wages. This aspect measures employee satisfaction with respect to the salary they receive and the existence of a salary increase, namely the amount of salary received in accordance with the level that is considered commensurate.
2. Promotion. This aspect measures the extent to which employee satisfaction relates to promotion policies and opportunities for promotion. Promotions or opportunities to improve careers also have an influence on employee job satisfaction.
3. Supervision (relationship with superiors). This aspect measures a person's job satisfaction with his superiors.
4. Additional Benefits. This aspect measures the extent to which individuals are satisfied with the additional benefits they receive from the organization.
5. Appreciation. This aspect measures the extent to which individuals are satisfied with the awards given based on work results.
6. Work Procedures and Regulations. This aspect measures satisfaction with respect to workplace procedures and regulations.
7. Work colleague. This aspect measures job satisfaction with regard to relationships with coworkers.
8. The Work Itself. Aspects that measure job satisfaction with matters relating to the work itself.
9. Communication. This aspect measures satisfaction related to communication that takes place at work.

Previous Research Review

Ihwana (2017) who examined the effect of compensation and work motivation on the loyalty of nurse apprentices in a case study conducted at the Iswahjudi Maospati Air Base Hospital, Magetan Regency. The population in this study were 145 people. The sampling technique in this study was purposive sampling so that 95 people were obtained. The data analysis technique used multiple linear regression analysis with the help of IBM SPSS Statistic version 20. The results showed that partially compensation had no significant effect on nurse apprentice loyalty, work motivation had a positive and significant effect on nurse apprentice loyalty, while simultaneously showed that compensation and work motivation effect on the loyalty of intern nurses.

Another study conducted by Virginia (2018) regarding the effect of physical workload on job satisfaction with job stress as a moderating variable. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of workload on job satisfaction with job stress as a moderating variable. The research was conducted at Gmim Pancaran Kasih General Hospital, Manado. The number of samples taken as many as 41 employees, with the saturated sample method. The method of collecting data is a survey with a questionnaire as a tool and interviews. Path analysis is used to obtain results so that it is found that workload has a positive effect on work stress, if the workload of employees increases, employee work stress will increase. Influential workload

negative on job satisfaction it shows if the workload increases then job satisfaction decreases, and vice versa. Job stress has a negative effect on job satisfaction. Work stress increases, job satisfaction decreases, and vice versa.

Maslichah (2016) in the journal the effect of work life balance and work environment on employee job satisfaction. The subjects in this study were nurses at Lavalette Hospital Malang with purposive sampling method, 63 respondents were used as research samples. The results showed that work life balance, physical work environment affect job satisfaction seen from the significance value of $F < 0.000 < 0.05$ and the adjusted R square value of 0.805. This shows that work life balance, physical work environment and non-physical work environment affect 80.5% of employee job satisfaction and the remaining 19.5% is influenced by other variables not included in the study.

Rizky Mauluddani Martaperdana (2019) who conducted a research entitled The Effect of Worklife Balance on Loyalty through Organizational Commitment as an Intervening Variable (Study at PT. Bank Mandiri Regional Office Bandung Branch). The level of work loyalty at PT. Bank Mandiri is in the good category. Worklife balance has a significant positive effect on work loyalty. The worklife balance also has a significant positive effect on commitment. Organizational commitment has a significant positive effect on loyalty to work. Worklife balance simultaneously affects work loyalty through organizational commitment, thus it can be said that there is an effect of worklife balance on work loyalty through organizational commitment.

Hypothesis

Based on the explanation above, the hypotheses in this study are:

1. It is suspected that workload affects nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
2. It is suspected that workload has an indirect effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
3. It is suspected that compensation has an effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
4. It is suspected that compensation has an indirect effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
5. It is suspected that work-life balance affects nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
6. It is suspected that work-life balance has an indirect effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.
7. It is suspected that job satisfaction has an effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital.

Research Model

Based on the description above, the research model can be described in the following chart

Figure 1 Research Model

Operational Definition of Research Variables

The following provides operational definitions of variables along with their indicators and the measurement scale used.

Table 2: Operational Definitions of Research Variables

No	Variable	Definition	Indicator	Scale
1	Employee Loyalty (Y ₂)	Loyalty is a willingness to protect and save one's physical and feelings (Robbin and Coulter, 2017)	1. Stay in the organization 2. Willing to be transferred anywhere, 3. Want to remain part of the organization, 4. Don't want to change professions 5. Willing to work beyond normal conditions, 6. Don't mind being given a tough task, 7. Proud to be a member of the organization 8. Accept whatever the organization does	ordinal
2	Compensation (X ₁)	Compensation is something that employees receive as	1. Wages 2. Wages	ordinal

		compensation for their achievements in carrying out their duties (Nurjaman, 2014)	3. Incentive 4. allowance 5. Facility	
3	Workload (X ₂)	Workload is the average activity frequency of each job within a certain period of time (Irwandy, 2017).	1. Variety of work to be done. 2. Target number of jobs to be completed 3. The level of difficulty of employees in completing tasks 4. There is a set time limit 5. There is under pressure to employees at work	ordinal
4	Work-Life Balance (X ₃)	Work-life balance is an individual's tendency to be truly committed to performing in every role he plays (Marks and MacDermid, 2011)	1. Time Balance 2. Engagement Balance 3. Balance of satisfaction both in the work environment and outside of work	ordinal
5	Job Satisfaction (Y ₂)	Job satisfaction is a person's attitude towards their services, that attitude comes from their perception of their work (Gibson, Ivancevich & Donnely, 2014)	1. Supervision (relationship with superiors). 2. Appreciation 3. Work procedures and rules 4. Work colleague 5. The work itself 6. Communication	ordinal

METHODS

Place and time of research

This research was conducted at Bangkinang Hospital which is located at Jalan Ring Roads Bangkinang-Batu Belah KM.01, Kumantan, Bangkinang District, Kampar Regency, Riau 28463. The study was conducted for 3 (three) months starting from May 2021 to August 2021.

Data Types and Sources

The types and sources of data used in the study are:

1. Primary Data, is research data obtained directly from the original source or data that has not been published by other parties.
2. Secondary Data, namely data obtained by researchers indirectly or data that has been published by other parties. This data can be obtained through literature, journals, and sources that support this research.

Data collection technique

The data collection techniques used are:

1. Questionnaires, namely data collection techniques carried out by providing a list of questions or questionnaires directly to the respondents.
2. Interviews, namely data collection techniques by conducting interviews with related parties such as leaders, personnel, employees and so on.
3. Research Files, namely data collection techniques carried out by browsing files or documents related to this research. Like data about a brief history of Bangkinang Hospital, employee data and other data relevant to this study.

Population and Sample

The population in this study were all employees of Bangkinang Hospital, totaling 271 employees. In this study, the determination of the number of samples was carried out using the Slovin formula, and the following results were obtained:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N e^2} = \frac{271}{1 + 271 (0.05)^2} = 161.5 \cong 162$$

Thus, the sample of this study amounted to 162 people, and the sampling was done by accidental random sampling method.

Data Analysis Tool

1. Validity and Reliability Test

Testing the reliability of all items or statements used in this study will use the Cronbach Alpha formula (Cronbach's alpha coefficient), which is generally considered reliable if the Cronbach's alpha value is > 0.6 (Hair. et. al., 2015). To get a value that is the level of reliability of the dimensions forming the latent variable, the formula is used:

$$\int \text{Construct Reliability} = \frac{(\sum \text{Standard Loading})^2}{(\sum \text{Standard Loading})^2 + \sum \epsilon_j}$$

Information :

- a. *Standard loading* obtained from standardized loading for each indicator obtained from the calculation results of AMOS 4.01
- b. ϵ_j is the measurement error of each indicator. Measurement error can be obtained from: $1 - (\text{Standard Loading})^2$

The validity test was carried out with the aim of knowing the accuracy and reliability of the questionnaire, which means that the questionnaire is able to measure what it should measure. The results of this test adequately reflect the topic being researched. The validity test was tested with the SPSS program by looking at the Pearsons Product Moment correlation for each statement item with a total test score. The equation to get the variance extract value is:

$$\int \text{Variance Extracted} = \frac{(\sum \text{Standard Loading})^2}{(\sum \text{Standard Loading})^2 + \sum \epsilon_j}$$

2. Data analysis

The research model that will be used in this study is a tiered structure model and to test the proposed hypothesis, the SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) analysis technique is used which is operated through the Smart PLS Version 3.00 program. After the theory or theoretical model is developed and described in a flowchart, the researcher can start converting the model specifications into a series of structural equations as follows:

$$Y1 = 1X1 + 2X2 + 3X3 + Z1$$

$$Y2 = 4X1 + 5X2 + 6X3 + 7Y1 + Z2$$

Description: Y1 = Job Satisfaction Y2 = Employee Loyalty

X1= Compensation X2 = Workload X3 = Work Life Balance

1- 7 = Regression Coefficient

The PLS approach is based on a shift in analysis from measuring model parameter estimates to measuring relevant predictive models. So that the focus of the analysis shifts from only estimation and interpretation of parameter significance to the validity and accuracy of predictions. Parameter estimation in PLS includes 3 things, namely: (Ghazali, 2006):

1. *Weight estimate* which is used to create the latent variable score.
2. The path estimate that relates the later variables and the loading estimate between the latent variables and their indicators.
3. *Means* and the location of the parameters (values of constants, regressions and intercepts for indicators and latent variables).

The following are the steps in the analysis with partial less squares, (Yamin, 2011):

1. The first step: designing a structural model (inner model). At this stage, the researcher formed a model of the relationship between the constructs.
2. Second step. Designing a measurement model (outer model). At this stage, the researcher defines and specifies the relationship between later constructs and their indicators, whether they are reflective or formative.
3. Third step. Construct path diagrams. The main function of building a path diagram is to visualize the relationship between indicators and their constructs and the relationship between constructs which makes it easier for researchers to see the model as a whole.
4. Step four. Model estimation. In this step, three weighting schemes are selected in the model estimation process, namely the factor weighting scheme, the centroid weighting scheme and the path weighting scheme.
5. Fifth step. Goodness of fit or model evaluation includes evaluation of measurement models and evaluation of structural models.
6. Step six, hypothesis testing and interpretation.

The following are the assessment criteria for the PLS model used by Chin 1998 in Ghazali (2011).

Table 3. PLS Assessment Criteria

Criteria	Explanation
Structural Model Evaluation	
R2 for endogenous variables	The results of R2 of 0.67, 0.33 and 0.19 for endogenous variables in the structural model identified that the moderators were "good", "moderate" and "weak".
Estimated path coefficient	The estimated value for the path relationship in the structural model must be significant. This significant value can be obtained by bootstrapping procedure.
F2 for effect size	The f2 values of 0.2, 0.15 and 0.35 can be interpreted whether the later variable predictor has a weak, medium or large influence on the structural level.
Evaluation of reflective measurement model	
<i>Loading factor</i>	Load factor value 0.70
<i>Composite Reliability</i>	<i>Composite reliability</i> measure internal consistency and the value must be above 0.60
<i>Average Variances Extracted</i>	Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value must be above 0.5
<i>Discriminant Validity</i>	The square root value of the AVE must be greater than the correlation value between the later variables.
<i>Cross loading</i>	Is another measure of discriminant validity. It is expected that each indicator block has a higher loading for each measured latent variable compared to indicators for other latent variables.
Evaluation of Formative Measurement Models	
<i>Significance of weight . value</i>	The estimated value for the formative measurement model must be significant. Significance level was assessed by bootstrapping procedure
<i>Multicollinearity</i>	The manifest variable in the block must be tested for multicol. The value of the variance inflation factor (VIF) can be used to test this. A VIF value above 10 indicates that there is multicollis.

RESEARCH RESULT

Respondent Identity

The characteristics of the samples obtained were based on gender, education, and length of work. The results of the questionnaire tabulation for the identity of the respondents can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Respondents Identity

Respondent Identity	Number of people)	Frequency (%)
Gender		
Woman	94	58.0
Man	68	45.0
Amount	162	100
Age		
Less than 25 years	3	1.9
25-35 Years	106	65.4
Over 35 Years	53	32.7
Amount	162	100
Level of education		
high school	7	4.3
Diploma	35	21.6
Bachelor	108	66.7
Master	12	7.4
Amount	162	100
Length of work		
Less 5 Years	62	38.3
5-10 Years	66	40.7
Over 10 Years	34	21.0

Amount	162	100
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Source: Data Processing Results

From Table 4 it can be seen that the majority of respondents in this study were female. This illustrates that the profession as a nurse is indeed widely cultivated by women in addition to the nature of the work that provides more services to patients. Then if you look at the age, the majority of the respondents in this study were in the age group of 25-35 years. This condition illustrates that the majority of nurses on duty at Bangkinang Hospital are still of productive age. From the results of respondents' responses, it is known that the majority of nurses are educated at the undergraduate level. This illustrates that nurses at Bangkinang Hospital are highly educated, this is certainly expected to have a positive impact on agency performance. Furthermore, it is seen how long the nurse has worked, From the results of the tabulation of the questionnaire data, it is known that the majority of respondents have worked between 5-10 years. This explains that nurses at Bangkinang Hospital have good work experience and it is hoped that the nurse's performance is also good.

Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

Nurse Loyalty Variable

Employee loyalty in this case is nurse loyalty, which is a sense of a nurse's loyal attitude at Bangkinang Hospital. Assessment of nurse loyalty is carried out using several indicators stated in several statements. Each statement is assessed using a Likert scale of 1-5. The results of the tabulation of respondents' responses to the nurse loyalty variable can be seen in Table 5.

If we look at Table 5, it is known that the total score of respondents' responses to the nurse loyalty variable is 3.92. This figure is in the good/loyal category. These results explain that nurses on duty at Bangkinang Hospital have a good level of loyalty. With the meaning of the word nurses will always want to be part of the hospital. This is evident for the responses of respondents stating that they will remain in the hospital no matter what happens.

Table 5. Respondents' Responses to Nurse Loyalty Variables

No	Statement		Alternative Answer					friday	Average
			5	4	3	2	1		
1	No matter what happens, I will persist to work in this hospital	F	56	51	49	6	0	162	3.97
		%	34.57	31.48	30.25	3.70	0.00	100	
		M	280	204	147	12	0	643	
2	I want to be transferred to another department, as long as I can still work at this hospital	F	38	70	49	5	0	162	3.87
		%	23.46	43.21	30.25	3.09	0.00	100	
		M	190	280	147	10	0	627	
3	I always want to always be a part of this hospital	F	47	58	56	1	0	162	3.93
		%	29.01	35.80	34.57	0.62	0.00	100	
		M	235	232	168	2	0	637	
4	With my current working conditions, I don't want to change jobs to other professions	F	52	44	62	4	0	162	3.89
		%	32.10	27.16	38.27	2.47	0.00	100	
		M	260	176	186	8	0	630	
5	I am willing to work more than normal working hours, as long as I can still work at this hospital	F	40	62	60	0	0	162	3.88
		%	24.69	38.27	37.04	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	200	248	180	0	0	628	
6	As a form of my loyalty to this hospital, I am willing to get a harder job than before	F	51	53	56	2	0	162	3.94
		%	31.48	32.72	34.57	1.23	0.00	100	
		M	255	212	168	4	0	639	
7	I am proud to be a member of this hospital	F	47	60	55	0	0	162	3.95
		%	29.01	37.04	33.95	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	235	240	165	0	0	640	
8		F	55	44	62	1	0	162	3.94
		%	33.95	27.16	38.27	0.62	0.00	100	

I can accept any policy made by the Bangkinang Hospital management	M	275	176	186	2	0	639	
Average Total Score								3.92
Criteria								Well

Source: Processed Data, 2021

Thus, it can be concluded that what is expected by a nurse, they have obtained at this hospital, so that they can achieve satisfaction with the work they are doing, and ultimately lead to high nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. This is expected to have a positive impact on the results achieved by the hospital in general.

Compensation Variable

Following are the responses of respondents to the statement of compensation.

Table 6: Respondents' Responses to Compensation Variables

No	Statement		Alternative Answer					friday	Average
			5	4	3	2	1		
1	Currently I get an adequate salary from Bangkinang Hospital	F	54	55	53	0	0	162	4.01
		%	33.33	33.95	32.72	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	270	220	159	0	0	649	
2	I receive wages paid monthly by the management of Bangkinang Hospital	F	50	59	52	1	0	162	3.98
		%	30.86	36.42	32.10	0.62	0.00	100	
		M	250	236	156	2	0	644	
3	I receive incentives if I work more than the working hours that are my obligation	F	61	45	53	3	0	162	4.01
		%	37.65	27.78	32.72	1.85	0.00	100	
		M	305	180	159	6	0	650	
4	In carrying out my duties, I also received allowances given by the management of the Bangkinang Hospital	F	45	57	58	2	0	162	3.90
		%	27.78	35.19	35.80	1.23	0.00	100	
		M	225	228	174	4	0	631	
5	In addition to salaries, incentives and allowances, the management of the Bangkinang Hospital also provides adequate facilities	F	51	49	61	1	0	162	3.93
		%	31.48	30.25	37.65	0.62	0.00	100	
		M	255	196	183	2	0	636	
Average Total Score								3.96	
Criteria								Well	

Source: Processed Data, 2021

From Table 6 it is known that the total score of respondents' responses to statements related to compensation is 3.96. This figure is in good criteria. This means that in general nurses stated that the compensation they received was in accordance with what they needed. This is certainly expected to have a positive impact on the achievement of the work of the nurse concerned, so that it also has a positive impact on improving the performance of the Bangkinang Hospital.

Workload

Assessment of the workload of nurses in this study was carried out using indicators stated in several statements. Following are respondents' responses to statements related to workload.

Table 7: Respondents' Responses to Workload Variables

No	Statement		Alternative Answer					friday	Average
			5	4	3	2	1		
1	I have a high workload because of the many variations of work I have to do	F	50	59	51	2	0	162	3.97
		%	30.86	36.42	31.48	1.23	0.00	100	

		M	250	236	153	4	0	643	
2	I have a high workload, because of the many work targets I have to complete	F	68	47	47	0	0	162	4.13
		%	41.98	29.01	29.01	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	340	188	141	0	0	669	
3	I have a high workload, because of my difficulty in completing the work that is my responsibility	F	58	47	57	0	0	162	4.01
		%	35.80	29.01	35.19	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	290	188	171	0	0	649	
4	I feel my workload is high because there is a time limit for each job that is my responsibility	F	41	71	50	0	0	162	3.94
		%	25.31	43.83	30.86	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	205	284	150	0	0	639	
5	I feel my workload is high, because I work under pressure from superiors	F	56	58	48	0	0	162	4.05
		%	34.57	35.80	29.63	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	280	232	144	0	0	656	
Average Total Score									4.02
Criteria									Well

Source: Processed Data, 2021

From the responses of respondents in Table 7 above, the average score of respondents' responses is 4.02. This figure is in the good category. This means that in general nurses at Bangkinang Hospital assume that the division of workload in this agency has been done well. Therefore, nurses are expected to be able to complete their respective work which has become their responsibility, so that what is expected by the leadership at this hospital can be realized.

Work-Life Balance

Assessment of respondents' responses to Work-Life Balance in this study was carried out using several statements and respondents' responses can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Respondents' Responses to Work-Life Balance

No	Statement		Alternative Answer					friday	Average
			5	4	3	2	1		
1	The Bangkinang Hospital where I work always provides enough rest time for employees	F	53	50	58	1	0	162	3.96
		%	32.72	30.86	35.80	0.62	0.00	100	
		M	265	200	174	2	0	641	
2	The leader always gives permission to employees, if there is a sudden need outside the main job	F	35	65	62	0	0	162	3.83
		%	21.60	40.12	38.27	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	175	260	186	0	0	621	
3	Leaders always involve subordinates for all social activities	F	54	57	50	1	0	162	4.01
		%	33.33	35.19	30.86	0.62	0.00	100	
		M	270	228	150	2	0	650	
4	Before formulating policies, leaders always ask for input from subordinates	F	47	51	63	1	0	162	3.89
		%	29.01	31.48	38.89	0.62	0.00	100	
		M	235	204	189	2	0	630	
5	Leaders always create conducive communication between superiors and subordinates	F	48	61	53	0	0	162	2.49
		%	29.63	37.65	32.72	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	240	244	159	0	0	403	
6	My working conditions match my previous expectations	F	50	47	65	0	0	162	3.91
		%	30.86	29.01	40.12	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	250	188	195	0	0	633	
Average Total Score									3.68
Criteria									Well

Source: Processed Data, 2021

From Table 8, it can be seen that the average score of respondents' responses to the Work-Life Balance variable is 3.68. This figure is in good criteria. This indicates that the nurse on duty at the Bangkinang Hospital said that they had or had found a Work-Life Balance between work and their personal life. This can have a positive impact on the achievement of the nurse's work.

Job satisfaction

The same thing was also carried out on the assessment of nurse job satisfaction at Bangkinang Hospital, and the results of the assessment on nurse job satisfaction are as shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Respondents' Responses to Job Satisfaction Variables

No	Statement	Alternative Answer					friday	Average	
		5	4	3	2	1			
1	In carrying out tasks, always get supervision from superiors	F	48	62	51	1	0	162	3.97
		%	29.63	38.27	31.48	0.62	0.00	100	
		M	240	248	153	2	0	643	
2	I feel satisfied at work, because the leadership always gives awards for the achievements of my work	F	49	52	61	0	0	162	3.93
		%	30.25	32.10	37.65	0.00	0.00	100	
		M	245	208	183	0	0	636	
3	I feel satisfied at work because there are clear procedures and rules as a guide in carrying out my duties	F	50	56	51	5	0	162	3.93
		%	30.86	34.57	31.48	3.09	0.00	100	
		M	250	224	153	10	0	637	
4	I feel satisfied at work, because there are good co-workers in my work team	F	46	51	64	1	0	162	3.88
		%	28.40	31.48	39.51	0.62	0.00	100	
		M	230	204	192	2	0	628	
5	I am satisfied with my current job because this job is in accordance with my wishes	F	52	51	57	2	0	162	3.94
		%	32.10	31.48	35.19	1.23	0.00	100	
		M	260	204	171	4	0	639	
6	I feel satisfied at work, because there is two-way communication in my workplace	F	50	53	58	1	0	162	3.94
		%	30.86	32.72	35.80	0.62	0.00	100	
		M	250	212	174	2	0	638	
Average Total Score								3.93	
Criteria								Well	

Source: Processed Data, 2021

From Table 9 it can be seen that the average score of respondents' responses is 3.93. This figure is in the good category, which means that in general the nurses at Bangkinang Hospital stated that they had a good fit at work. This is expected to increase the achievement of the nurse's work, so that the nurse's loyalty to this hospital can be increased.

Validity and Reliability Test Results

The results of testing the validity of the research variables can be seen in Table 10:

Table 10: Research Variable Validity Test Results

Variable	Items	r count	Significance	Information
Loyalty	Statement 1	0.499	0.000	Valid
	Statement 2	0.277	0.000	Valid
	Statement 3	0.327	0.000	Valid
	Statement 4	0.392	0.000	Valid
	Statement 5	0.154	0.051	Invalid
	Statement 6	0.335	0.000	Valid
	Statement 7	0.397	0.000	Valid
	Statement 8	0.415	0.000	Valid
Compensation	Statement 1	0.458	0.000	Valid
	Statement 2	0.528	0.000	Valid
	Statement 3	0.570	0.000	Valid

	Statement 4	0.456	0.000	Valid
	Statement 5	0.157	0.046	Valid
Workload	Statement 1	0.537	0.000	Valid
	Statement 2	0.332	0.000	Valid
	Statement 3	0.576	0.000	Valid
	Statement 4	0.437	0.000	Valid
	Statement 5	0.376	0.000	Valid
<i>Work-Life Balance</i>	Statement 1	0.501	0.000	Valid
	Statement 2	0.342	0.000	Valid
	Statement 3	0.412	0.000	Valid
	Statement 4	0.570	0.000	Valid
	Statement 5	0.405	0.000	Valid
	Statement 6	0.531	0.000	Valid
Job satisfaction	Statement 1	0.483	0.000	Valid
	Statement 2	0.341	0.000	Valid
	Statement 3	0.273	0.000	Valid
	Statement 4	0.460	0.000	Valid
	Statement 5	0.526	0.000	Valid
	Statement 6	0.523	0.000	Valid

Source: Processed Data, 2021

From Table 10 it is known that the employee/nurse loyalty variable formed from eight statements, after processing the data, it is known that the fifth statement is declared invalid, because it has a r hinting significance value higher than alpha ($\alpha = 0.05$). Thus the nurse loyalty variable is only formed from 7 statements. Furthermore, for other variables, namely compensation, workload, work-life balance and job satisfaction, from the results of data processing, it is known that all statement items are declared valid. Because all statement items from each variable have a significance value of r arithmetic which is lower than alpha ($\alpha = 0.05$).

All statements that are declared valid, need to be tested for reliability. It aims to determine the level of reliability of all valid items for each variable. The results of reliability testing can be seen in Table 11.

Table 11: Reliability Test Results

No	Variable	Alpha Cronbach`s	Information
1	Nurse Loyalty	0.654	Reliable/Reliable
2	Compensation	0.772	Reliable/Reliable
3	Workload	0.811	Reliable/Reliable
4	<i>Work-Life Balance</i>	0.865	Reliable/Reliable
5	Job satisfaction	0.747	Reliable/Reliable

Source: Processed Data, 2021

From Table 11, it can be seen that the cronbach's alpha value of all the variables studied, namely nurse loyalty, compensation, workload, work-life balance and job satisfaction has a cronbach's alpha value above 0.5. These results explain that all valid items have a good level of reliability in determining variable values.

Hypothesis Testing Results

After passing the validity and reliability tests, further testing is carried out on the model that will be used in hypothesis testing. The evaluation was carried out comparing the AVE root value with the correlation between the constructs. The recommended result is that the AVE root value should be higher than the correlation between constructs (Yamin and Kurniawan, 2011).

The model has better discriminant validity if the square root of the AVE for each construct is greater than the correlation between the two constructs in the model. A good AVE value is required to have a value greater than 0.50. In this study, the value of AVE and the square root of AVE for each construct can be shown in Table 12:

Table 12: Value of AVE and Square Root of AVE

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Loyalty	0.917	0.912	0.913	0.822

Job satisfaction	0.756	0.821	0.944	0.819
Workload	0.835	0.780	0.873	0.683
Compensation	0.819	0.662	0.855	0.585
WLB	0.781	0.862	0.812	0.752

Source: Processed Data, 2021

Based on Table 12, all constructs show an AVE value greater than 0.50, with the smallest value being 0.585 for the compensation variable. This value has met the requirements in accordance with the specified minimum AVE value limit of 0.50. After knowing the value of the square root of the AVE for each construct, the next step is to compare the square root of the AVE with the correlation between the constructs in the model. In this study, the results of the correlation between constructs and the square root value of AVE can be shown in Table 13 below:

Table 13: Correlation value between constructs and the value of the square root of AVE

	Loyalty	Job satisfaction	Workload	Compensation	WLB
Loyalty	0.863				
Job satisfaction	0.495	0.634			
Workload	0.693	0.542	0.430		
Compensation	0.635	0.850	0.218	0.951	
WLB	0.726	0.681	0.358	0.871	0.861

Source: Processed Data, 2021

Table 13 shows that the AVE square root value for each construct is greater than the correlation value, so that the construct in this research model can still be said to have good discriminant validity. The outer model can be measured in addition to assessing convergent validity and discriminant validity, it can also be done by looking at construct reliability or latent variables as measured by composite reliability values. The construct is declared reliable if the composite reliability has a value > 0.7 , then the construct is declared reliable. The SmartPLS output results for the composite reliability value can be shown in Table 14:

Table 14: Composite Reliability Value

	Composite Reliability
Loyalty	0.836
Job satisfaction	0.861
Workload	0.856
Compensation	0.866
WLB	0.785

Source: Processed Data, 2021

From the results of the SmartPLS output in Table 14, the composite reliability value for all constructs is above the value of 0.70. With the resulting value, all constructs have good reliability in accordance with the minimum value limit that has been required. After testing the outer model that has met, the next step is testing the inner model (structural model). The inner model can be evaluated by looking at the r-square (reliability indicator) for the dependent construct and the t-statistical value of the path coefficient test. The higher the r-square value, the better the prediction model of the proposed research model. The path coefficients value indicates the level of significance in hypothesis testing. Analysis of Variant (R²) or Test of Determination can be shown in Table 15:

Table 15: R-square . value

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Loyalty	0.856	0.738

Source: Processed Data, 2021

Based on the R-square value in Table 15, it shows that workload, compensation, work-life balance and job satisfaction are able to explain the variability of the nurse loyalty construct of 73.8%, and the remaining 26.2% is explained by other constructs outside those studied in this study. Hypothesis testing is carried out based on the results of the Inner Model (structural model) test which includes r-square output, parameter coefficients and t-statistics. To see whether a hypothesis can be accepted or rejected, among others, by paying attention to the significance value between constructs, t-statistics,

and p-values. The hypothesis testing of this research was carried out with the help of the SmartPLS (Partial Least Square) 3.0 software. These values can be seen from the bootstrapping results. The rule of thumb used in this research is t-statistic > 1.96 with a significance level of p-value 0.05 (5%) and the beta coefficient is positive. The value of testing the hypothesis of this study can be shown in Table 16

Table 16: Path Coefficients Hasil Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Workload -> Job Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.031	0.003	0.046	0.670	0.503
Compensation -> Job Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.024	0.007	0.060	3.399	0.001
WLB -> Job Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.075	0.034	0.074	3.012	0.012
Workload -> Job Satisfaction	-0.137	-0.010	0.202	2,678	0.018
Workload -> Loyalty	-0.149	-0.136	0.189	2,790	0.013
Job Satisfaction -> Loyalty	0.223	0.143	0.195	3.142	0.011
Compensation -> Job Satisfaction	0.108	0.011	0.262	2.412	0.041
Compensation -> Loyalty	0.206	0.061	0.228	1.906	0.036
WLB -> Job Satisfaction	0.338	0.095	0.321	2.051	0.024
WLB -> Loyalty	0.275	0.209	0.276	2,067	0.031

Source: Processed Data, 2021

The first hypothesis examines whether the workload of nurses has a direct effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The test results show the leadership beta coefficient on employee performance is -0.149 and the t-statistic is 2.790 and p-values are 0.013. The results of this test prove that there is a significant effect of the workload variable on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital, so the first hypothesis is accepted. The second hypothesis tests whether workload has an indirect effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The test results show that the beta coefficient of workload through job satisfaction on nurse loyalty is 0.031 and the t-statistic is 0.670 and p-values is 0.503. From these results it is stated that the p-value is greater than alpha, namely $0.503 > 0.05$. This proves that there is no indirect effect of workload on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital, thus the second hypothesis is rejected. The third hypothesis tests whether compensation has an effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The test results show that the beta coefficient of compensation on nurse loyalty is 0.206 and the t-statistic is 1.906 and p-values are 0.036. From these results it is stated that the p-value is lower than alpha, namely $0.036 < 0.05$. This proves that compensation has a significant effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. Thus the third hypothesis is accepted. The fourth hypothesis tests whether compensation has a significant indirect effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The test results show the beta coefficient of compensation through job satisfaction on nurse loyalty is 0.024 and the t-statistic is 3.399 and p-values is 0.001. From these results it is stated that the p-value is lower than alpha, namely $0.001 < 0.05$. This proves that compensation has a significant indirect effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. Thus the fourth hypothesis is accepted.

The fifth hypothesis tests whether *work-life balance* on the loyalty of nurses at Bangkinang Hospital. The test results show the value of the beta . coefficient *work-life balance* to nurse loyalty is 0.275 and t-statistic is 2.067 and p-values is 0.0067. From these results, it is stated that the p-value is lower than alpha, namely $0.067 < 0.05$. This proves that *work-life balance* significant effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. Thus the fifth hypothesis is accepted. The sixth hypothesis tests whether *work-life balance* indirectly affect the loyalty of nurses at Bangkinang Hospital. The test results show the value of the beta . coefficient *work-life balance* through job satisfaction to nurse loyalty of 0.075 and t-statistics that is equal to 3.012 and p-values of 0.012. From these results, it is stated that the p-value is lower than alpha, namely $0.012 < 0.05$. This proves that *work-life balance* has a significant indirect effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. Thus the sixth hypothesis is accepted.

The seventh hypothesis tests whether Job satisfaction has an effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The test results show the value of the beta . coefficient job satisfaction to nurse loyalty is 0.223 and the t-statistic is 3.142 and p-values are 0.011. From these results, it is stated that the p-value is lower than alpha, namely $0.011 < 0.05$. This proves that job satisfactions significant effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. Thus the seventh hypothesis is accepted. The results of testing the hypothesis can also be presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Path Analysis Results

In summary, the results of hypothesis testing can be seen in Table 17 below.

Table 17: Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis		Results	Information
H1	It is suspected that workload affects nurse loyalty	1= -0.149 t-stat = 2,790 (0.013)	Hypothesis Accepted
H2	It is suspected that workload has an indirect effect on nurse loyalty	2= 0.031 t-stat = 0.670 (0.503)	Hypothesis Rejected
H3	It is suspected that compensation has an effect on nurse loyalty	3= 0.108 t-stat = 2,412 (0.041)	Hypothesis Accepted
H4	It is suspected that compensation has an indirect effect on nurse loyalty	4= 0.042 t-stat = 3399 (0.001)	Hypothesis Accepted
H5	It is suspected that work-life balance affects nurse loyalty	5= 0.275 t-stat = 2,067 (0.031)	Hypothesis Accepted
H6	It is suspected that work-life balance has an indirect effect on nurse loyalty	6= 0.075 t-stat = 3.012 (0.012)	Hypothesis Accepted
H7	It is suspected that job satisfaction has an effect on nurse loyalty	7= 0.223 t-stat = 3.142 (0.012)	Hypothesis Accepted

DISCUSSION

The problem of low levels of employee loyalty can occur in any organization. Is it an organization whose focus is profit-making or even an organization whose focus is on social enterprises. The issue of loyalty in an organization, often has a negative impact on the organization. The high level of employee turnover, because employees are easy to leave (leaving the organization) and it is also easy to accept new employees. This low employee loyalty will ultimately harm the company in every way. The phenomenon that occurs in government organizations, state apparatus (PNS), low loyalty is not a new issue, but a long journey that keeps happening. The impacts that arise due to low loyalty include the emergence of deviant behavior from employees.

Negative behaviors that are intentionally carried out as a form of their disappointment because they are not satisfied with their work. Deliberately coming to the office late, intentionally damaging office assets or property, bringing home office items without the permission of the leadership, doing work that is not related to his duties and authorities for personal interests, leaving the office within office hours and many other behaviors- deviant behavior as a manifestation of low loyalty.

In this study, it is known that there is a suitability of the characteristics of respondents with research variables, for example, the age of respondents in working establishments aged 25-35 years is known to be 106 people or 65.4%, so ideally they have high loyalty, while from the level of education it is known that the number of nurses with undergraduate education is a number of 108 people or 66.7% so that employees are quite reliable in their productive age, if managed optimally and with the right strategy, it can certainly increase loyalty from time to time. In terms of tenure or work experience, it is

known that there are 66 novice employees who have worked for less than 5 years while the rest are established (productive) employees who have high work experience, meaning that they have the enthusiasm to continue to find the most effective way of working.

Various efforts have been made by the leadership elements so that employee loyalty continues to increase which in the end can be in accordance with the expectations of the organization. In terms of compliance with every staffing and service regulation, attendance and return compliance has been carried out with electronic absent record data, also every nurse at the beginning of the year is required to prepare Employee Work Targets (SKP) which guides their main duties. Every day, employees are required to make a daily report on what was done on that day, starting at work until coming home from work. Besides that, every morning before going to work, morning apples are held and briefings from the leadership elements to employees, how this land agency can always improve services for the better.

There are still many services that are not completed on time. This is inseparable from the government's policy that in the last 5 years there has been no new employee acceptance, while the number of employees who are retiring continues to grow and in 2020 there are 10 people entering retirement. On the other hand, the workload continues to increase from time to time, so an employee must handle workloads beyond his capacity. Therefore, one of the benefits of this research is that it will provide valuable information to assist leaders in making decisions. In this study, a model has been tested which explains that low loyalty will be revived through job satisfaction. Job satisfaction for employees is important, because high job satisfaction will have a positive impact on employees, especially in terms of loyalty. If the various expectations of employees when doing work can be met in the work itself, then job satisfaction will arise. Therefore, efforts to continue to increase satisfaction until the optimal point is reached need to be done. The model in this study also explained that job satisfaction can be increased through the concept of workload and work environment.

Workload and compensation and work life-balance are two things that are outside the employee's self, but are felt by the employee. What an employee does may be in accordance with the job description. Unfortunately, job descriptions often do not accommodate all aspirations related to an employee's job. This causes employees to do work beyond what is actually their obligation and responsibility.

Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that the workload for each employee was responded to with a different assessment. There are most employees who feel the workload is too heavy, some feel it is still quite light. Whereas the heavy or light workload of each employee is influenced by, among other things, the main tasks of each function, where each main task of the function is highly dependent on the service request from the service user community. So that at certain times the main tasks of the function, such as service A, the workload is very heavy (the volume is large), while service B is very light and at other times it can be the other way around.

Employees are generally responsible for what are the main tasks of their function. The responsibility of these employees seems very clear that they devote all their abilities and expertise so that tasks can be completed on time. Besides that, there is good cooperation between fellow employees to help each other. Employees seem to feel light and happy in carrying out their responsibilities, this can be seen by many employees who come to work early and leave after office hours, solely doing their responsibilities, even work that has not been completed is brought home to be done at home. The employee's actions are in accordance with the wishes of each employee without any orders from superiors and there is no additional for overtime, the employee only wants to complete what is his responsibility. From all the perceptions of these employees, it can be concluded that the workload is indeed a driving force for loyalty actions. The same applies to compensation and work-life balance in hospitals. It has become a common thing, everywhere most government offices get less attention.

Lack of attention from superiors on service applications that tend to change and have many problems. Existing service applications should be repaired and added to the shortcomings, not replaced and replaced with new programs. While the supporting equipment and employees have not been prepared in advance. So that it is necessary to procure supporting tools and training of employees for its operations, this takes time while the service must not stop. This puts pressure on employees how to be able to adapt to change and at the same time serve.

The results of this study indicate that workload has a direct effect on job satisfaction and job satisfaction has a direct effect on loyalty. While the workload does not directly affect loyalty. This means that loyalty can be increased through improving the workload if the workload itself can provide job satisfaction. So workload can affect loyalty but not directly. The loyalty of nurses/employees is shown by the commitment of employees within the institution, commitment to the organization can be formed due to several factors, both from the organization and the individual itself (Fathiya, 1014). So in the multivariate test, this study shows that there is an effect of job satisfaction on loyalty with a significant value.

The physiological needs of nurses in hospitals can be met by looking at the results of the study, most of which state that the compensation received is sufficient. While the need for security in this case is living in the future, namely a career path where some nurses state that their perception of their career path is good. The results of this study are relevant to the results of research by Pratama (2014), Muhammad (2016), Juliani (2016) which states that compensation has a positive

effect on loyalty. Murty (2011) said that the basis for retaining employees is by providing compensation. Meanwhile, according to Hasibuan (2011) compensation is able to meet the needs of life and be able to improve their welfare. So that when they receive it is able to meet their needs, they will survive.

The results of the bivariate analysis of the relationship between workload and nurse loyalty have a p value = 0.013, which means that there is a significant relationship between workload and nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The application of workloads is able to make employees bring out their full potential. Tarwaka (2010) states that workload is defined as a difference between the capacity or ability of workers and the demands of the work that must be faced. Robbins (1007) states that the positive and negative of a person's workload depends on the perception of each individual. Steers in (Kusumo, 2006) states that the factors that cause loyalty include job characteristics, in the form of work challenges, job stress, interaction opportunities and job compatibility. But in this study, the results showed that there was no relationship between workload and loyalty. This situation can be caused because there are other factors that are more dominant, namely related to satisfaction. Where the level of nurse satisfaction reaches 62.5%, one of the factors that causes satisfaction is the provision of compensation.

When a person has a lot of demands for his work but gets compensation that is deemed sufficient, the nurse will feel fair so that they maintain their loyalty. These results are the same as the research conducted by Beheshti (2015). The results of the multivariate study obtained a sig value of 0.503 so it can be concluded that there is no effect of workload on nurse loyalty. This study is not comparable to research conducted by Joyce (2017) which states that one of the causes of burnout is fatigue. One of the causes of workload not having an effect on loyalty is the existence of compensation that is deemed sufficient, such as research conducted by Siboro (2012) and Dharmawan (2010) which states that compensation can have a strong influence on employee loyalty.

The results of the bivariate analysis of the relationship between compensation and nurse loyalty have a p value = 0.000 which means that there is a significant relationship between compensation and nurse loyalty. Dessler (2015) states that compensation includes all forms of payment given to employees. The purpose of giving compensation is to retain employees, a form of justice and appreciation for employees (Handoko, 2008). Rahmadana (2015) states that if the compensation is managed properly and correctly, the level of employee loyalty to the company will increase, because if loyalty decreases it will harm the company.

The study identified by Dwija et al (1014) said that to know the loyalty of employees to the company can be seen from the compensation given by the company to employees. This study is in line with research conducted by Hassan (2013) which resulted in a correlation between compensation and loyalty. Compensation is an award given to employees as remuneration or contributions that employees give to the agency (Panggabean, 2011). So that compensation is an important factor that hospitals need to pay attention to in order to retain their employees.

In the multivariate analysis, it was found that compensation has an influence on loyalty, it can be seen from the results of the sig value of 0.036 so that it is stated that there is an effect of compensation on loyalty. Muhammad (2016), shows that compensation has a positive effect on employee performance which leads to job satisfaction so that loyalty will increase. This is in line with research conducted by Juliani (2015) which states that compensation has a positive influence on employee loyalty. Duxburry & Higgins (in Mayangsari & Amalia, 2018) suggest that the involvement of women in the world of work places a double burden on her as a woman. Women were asked to commit to their work like men, while at the same time they had to give priority to the role of the family as housewives. Furthermore, other studies have shown that women also experience lower partner support regarding their careers than their male counterparts (Meenakshi, Subrahmanyam, & Ravichandran, 2013). The dual role of career women will become a conflict if management is not carried out properly (Ermawati, 2016). Career women who play multiple roles need to strike a balance between life and work.

Wei, Yili & Tian (2013) stated that individuals who have a high work-life balance will easily enjoy job and family satisfaction and have little intention to quit their job. When work-life balance practices are reduced and work and personal demands are increasing, this can be one of the triggers for more rapid stress. So, work-life balance will result in employee loyalty at work

CONCLUSION

The results of research and testing prove that there is a significant effect of the workload variable on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The results of research and testing prove that there is no indirect effect of workload on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The results of research and testing prove that compensation has a significant effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The results of research and testing prove that compensation has a significant indirect effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The results of research and testing prove that *work-life balance* significant effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The results of research and testing prove that *work-life balance* indirect significant

effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital. The results of research and testing prove that job satisfaction has a significant effect on nurse loyalty at Bangkinang Hospital

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